

ISic3393

I.Sicily inscription 3393

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific; building
(?)

Material

limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.11.13 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Soluntum

Place of origin (modern)

Solunto

Provenance

found in the agora, to the south of the large cistern, 25.05.1954

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Solunto, Area Archeologica e
Antiquarium di Solunto

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR137125

1. ἐπ [ὶ ---]

2. ἦ [---]

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645611

EDR 137125

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 58.1055.1

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